

Project acronym: BETTER Life

Title: Bringing Excellence to Transformative Socially Engaged Research in Life Sciences through Integrated Digital Centers

Project number: 101071314

Deliverable 3.2

BETTER Life Toolkits

Description: Socially engaged research toolkits for life sciences. In line with the identified standards for SER in LS, toolkits allow to upskilling early career researchers on SER in LS (individual level upskilling) and, at the same time, upskilling partner university staff on SER in LS (institutional level upskilling).

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
DCoE	Digital Center of Excellence
ECR	Early Career Researcher
EU	European Union
HEI	Higher Education Institution
(H)EIL	(Human) Ecosystem Integration Lab
LS	Life Sciences
NGO	Non-governmental organization
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
SER	Socially Engaged Research
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
STEM	Science Technology Engineering Mathematics

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report aims to introduce and explain the Toolkits that will allow to achieve the previously identified Standards for socially engaged research in life sciences, both on an individual and institutional level. The report builds on the Framework for Socially Engaged Research (SER) in life sciences (LS) in the BETTER Life project and on the D3.2 Report on Standards. It is the basis for developing the activities of WP4 (Capacity Building and Community of Practice).

This report is organised in two sections. The first section presents background information, including key concept definitions, while also discussing the purpose of the toolkits and the methodology used for their development. The second section presents an overview of the toolkits, providing background information about their specific objectives, target groups, expected outcomes, etc., according to a jointly-set up template.

The toolkits outlined in this report will be further developed and operationalised through their implementation and use during WP4 activities. The toolkits will thus turn the standards into real and tangible achievements, fostering SER in life sciences.

At the same time, to ensure the quality and effectiveness of the toolkits, it was crucial to consolidate the tools and activities into a cohesive framework. By developing the standards, we have ensured the integrity and value of the toolkits here presented as a major output of the project. These toolkits will serve as practical resources, supporting the activities carried out by researchers, institutions, and other stakeholders involved in SER in life sciences. With the toolkits, we envision empowering end users to apply the standards in a way that suits their specific needs and contexts.

1. INTRODUCTION

The first section introduces important background details and defines key concepts. Additionally, it delves into the significance of the toolkits, explaining their purpose, and offers insights into the development process of their creation.

1.1 The Origin of Toolkits from the Framework and Standards for SER in Life Sciences of the BETTER Life Project

The BETTER Life is based on the Quadruple Helix model of innovation, where the interaction of academics, research, industry, government, and civil society generate mutually beneficial partnerships. The BETTER Life project aims to assist ECRs in designing and conducting research in collaboration with and between Quadruple Helix actors. This aspect emphasises the importance of involving ECRs in meaningful engagement with academia, industry, government, and civil society to enhance the impact of their research. By supporting ECRs in navigating and leveraging the Quadruple Helix model and equipping them with the necessary tools and guidance, the project seeks to empower them to create research that aligns with real-world needs, contributes to community involvement in research, and ensures that the research initiatives have a tangible impact on addressing pressing challenges.

In previous deliverables, we consistently established numerous fundamental definitions relating to the problem. Building upon this foundation, we now introduce a Toolkit definition that was absent in the prior deliverables since it becomes relevant right now.

Toolkit: a toolkit is a modeled and guided way to implement and develop activities of SER in LS. It can assume different forms: from handbooks/guidelines to multi-player and virtual games, from trainings to online systems and platforms designed to support the research activities of early career researchers in LS. The purpose of the toolkits for SER in LS is to support the research activities of early career researchers in LS, fostering a collaborative approach to research that, starting from considering societal needs, aims in general to have a meaningful societal impact. In selecting the tools to be developed, we

followed the findings from the examples of good practice and the consultations. The following factors emerged as challenges or successful strategies: communication, presentation and involvement of the stakeholders of the Quadruple Helix.

The framework for socially engaged research in life sciences has four dimensions (numbered 1 to 4) and twelve sub-dimensions (with corresponding standards) as followed:

1. **Institutional Environment** standard with sub-dimensions of 1.1 Supporting structures, 1.2. Research capacities, and 1.3. Contextual knowledge,
2. **Stakeholders Engagement** standard with sub-dimensions of 2.1 Involvement of societal stakeholders, 2.2 Networking and collaboration, and 2.3. Shared power,
3. **Relevance** standard with sub-dimensions of 3.1 Contextual relevance, 3.2 Scientific relevance, and 3.3 Quality assurance measures,
4. **Impacts** standard with sub-dimensions of 4.1 Instrumental benefits, 4.2 Conceptual outcomes, and 4.3 Enhanced ecosystem capacities.

More information is in the Deliverable 3.1 Standards for Socially Engaged Research in Life Sciences, available at: <https://betterlifehorizon.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/D3.1-Standards-for-Socially-Engaged-Research-in-Life-Sciences.pdf>. All four (4) standards and all twelve (12) sub-dimensions are represented in the proposed toolkits.

1.2 Toolkits' Development

The methodology employed in developing the toolkits for SER closely mirrors the methodology used in creating the standards for SER, as the former builds upon the latter. Hence, the toolkits outlined in this report were developed using a two-stage participative methodology combined with a desk research approach.

In the initial stage of the participative method, a co-creation workshop was organised, bringing together the BETTER Life project consortium partners with experience in life sciences. Through the utilisation of brainstorming and mind-mapping exercises, the consortium partners identified the toolkits that align with the pre-established standards for SER within the BETTER Life Project (Figures 1).

The altogether of thirty-five (35) toolkits were identified and organised according into six (6) groups: (i) Online platforms – webpages, (ii) Guidelines, (iii) Trainings, (iv) Games, (v) Reverse tools, and (vi) Other tools. These thirty-six (36) toolkits were refined according to a review of relevant information (columns of Table 1): Tool-how, Description, Target group,

Standard, Difficulty in development, Complexity, Generality, Need to customise, Special field, Novelty factor, and Costs.

Name / Idea / what	Tool - how	Description	Target group	Standard
Supporting institutional structures	Showcase & guidelines	How to implement supporting institutional structures	Institution	1.1,
Engagement facilitator	Showcase & guidelines	How to implement an engagement facilitator?	Institution	1.2,
Communication of science / research projects	Guidelines	Easy guide with simple and clear tips on how to deliver sectorial, complex and scientific topics to citizens and other stakeholders Step-by-Step Guide on how to approach, consult, cooperate and discuss with QH actors from the viewpoint of researchers/ECR. A detailed guidelines handbook with ~30-50 pages with illustrations, examples of various methods for engagement etc.	ECR	2.3, 4.2
Community preparedness (or resilience) model	Handbook	A guide on how to develop an assessment of community preparedness (or resilience) to possible disasters through semi-structured interviews to key stakeholders, and then how to start a co-creation process to strengthen resilience capacity through co-designed strategies and action plans	ECR, Institution	1.2, 1.3, 2.1, 2.2, 2.3
Interaction of natural and societal networks Supporting interaction of community, science, and governance	Method / guidelines / research approach	Three steps research approach in raising the quality of interacting natural and societal networks. The scientific research approach including three (3) steps in enhancing integration of natural and societal networks in urban / per-urban / extra-urban contexts: (i) Analyze stakeholder perspectives to understand their arguments (ii) Analyze and utilization of (local) knowledge from ecological / societal / planning points of views (iii) Identify and explore innovative governance options for enhancing natural-societal relations in landscape	ECR, Institution	1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 2.1., 3.2, 4.2,

Figure 1. First list of possible toolkits envisioned by the consortium partners and divided into six (6) categories: Online platforms, Guidelines, Trainings, Games, Reverse tools, and Other tools.

As the preparation for the second stage of the participative methodology, the consortium conducted preference voting from the wide list of thirty-six (36) to recognise the ten (10) most promising tools for further implementation.

Figure 2a and 2b. Shortlist of ten (10) toolkits, selected by consortium partners through an online voting system and the coverage of standards with the proposed toolkits.

In the second stage of the participative methodology, another workshop involving the consortium partners was held to finetune and validate the developed toolkits (Figures 3, 4,

and 5). The methodology employed facilitated the collaborative co-creation of toolkits by consortium partners from nine institutions, drawing on existing knowledge and validating their alignment with the objectives of the BETTER Life project.

Figure 3. Coverage of standards and sub-dimensions by the ten (10) proposed tools.

All BETTER Life partners contributed to the development of the toolkits and spread the leadership, contribution, and interest in developing selected toolkits.

Figure 4. Preliminary result of the collaborative workshop to define responsibilities and contributions for the further development and elaboration of the ten (10) selected toolkits.

In the final stage of defining responsibilities and contributions, each of the nine (9) consortium partners is assigned to one of ten (10) selected toolkits.

Tool	LEAD	Contribution
1 Supporting Interaction of Community, Science and Governance	EMU	ACEEU; MLU; UNICAM
2 Design Thinking	UNICAM	MLU
3 Promote your Research Communication	EDUCONS	ACEEU; DU
4 Simulation/ Role Play-Game: Training	MLU	EMU
5 HEI Innovate – Self Reflection Tool	ACEEU	HELIXCONNECT; CZU
6 Visual methodologies for Landscape Observatory	UNICAM	EMU; PULS
7 Mentorship programme	DU	PULS
8 (Human) Ecosystem Integration Lab: Platform	HELIXCONNECT	EDUCONS
9 Academic Bridge	CZU	EDUCONS; HELIXCONNECT
10 R Shiny Application Suite – Platform, Webpage	PULS	HELIXCONNECT; CZU
Difficulty in Development: red=high, blue=medium, green=low		

Figure 5. Final list of 10 toolkits with related responsibilities and contributions.

Only UNICAM partner is leading development and implementation of two (2) toolkits. Each of partners contribute to at least additional two tools to assure the most quality implementation of further activities.

2. OVERVIEW AND STRUCTURE OF THE TOOLKITS

The elaboration of the toolkits was accomplished through collaborative workshops involving participatory brainstorming sessions, comprehensive mapping and voting exercises for progressive selection among the consortium partners. These efforts culminated in the creation of 10 toolkits, as summarized in Figure 5 (see above).

The toolkits are matching one or more of the 12 standards previously identified, which are their “guiding stars”. The insights gathered during the toolkits’ development workshops were carefully consolidated and further expanded into 10 descriptive templates, one for each toolkit, which will be presented in the subsequent section.

2.1 Toolkits for Socially Engaged Research in Life Sciences

The toolkits for socially engaged research are conceived as a practical guide that will adapt and evolve alongside the development of new needs in life science research and the society. These toolkits should be interpreted as versatile methods and approaches for conducting research in the field of life sciences. In line with the corresponding standards, the toolkits encompass essential aspects such as “what,” “who,” and “how,” addressing key questions and offering practical tools that can assist early career researchers in improving their research methods and strategies.

Toolkit n. 1

Supporting Interaction of Community, Science and Governance

Type: Guidelines

Matching Standard(s): 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 2.1, 3.2, 4.2

Responsibility: EMU

Authors: Anton Shkaruba, Ana Sopina, Flavio Stimilli

Short description	<p>The aim of the tool is to support spatial/urban planning process based on the understanding of citizens' perception of landscape quality expressed in qualitative or quantitative terms.</p> <p>Tool: a guideline for measuring the perception of landscape quality by citizens with suggestions for integrating the results to spatial planning policies and designs.</p>
Target group(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early Career Researcher (ECR) • University Members • Quadruple Helix Actors <p>- specifically the actors involved to spatial planning</p>
Benefit for target group(s)	<p>Early Career Researcher (ECR)</p> <p>A better understanding of the spatial planning process and how citizens could be involved to it in an inclusive manner.</p> <p>A better overview of how Quadruple Helix actors judge, engage with and address certain societal challenges.</p> <p>University Members</p> <p>A tool to interactively design a practical seminar during their lecture series.</p> <p>An engaging way to teach young students about various goals, agendas and individual targets among important and influential societal stakeholders involved to the spatial planning.</p>

	<p>Quadruple Helix Actors</p> <p>A tool supporting inclusive and engaging spatial planning, helping citizens to formulate their preferences regarding the quality of landscapes, and to the actors implementing the planning process to understand the preferences of citizens.</p>
<p>Measures</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collecting and adopting the methods for quantitative and qualitative evaluation of the quality of landscapes by citizens (such as suggested by Hisschemoller et al, 2022, http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2022.104021). • Developing recommendations for integrating the evaluation(s) to the inclusive planning process.
<p>Expected outcome(s)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Once the guidelines will be completed, they will be disseminated to target actors and also tested in a selected community with ongoing spatial planning process. • Feedback surveys will be conducted after disseminating and testing the guidelines. • It is expected that the guidelines will contribute to the development of transparent and inclusive planning process.
<p>Specific activities and resources required</p>	<p>Writeshop and consultations with stakeholders</p> <p>To design the guidelines a writeshop by members of the development group is envisioned; once the guidelines are finished, a consultation round with local stakeholders is planned to get a feedback first hand.</p> <p>Testing round</p> <p>The guidelines will be tested in a community with ongoing planning process.</p> <p>Feedback Surveys and Refinement</p> <p>Once the trials are done and all the feedback is received, the guidelines can be refined and improved.</p> <p>Dissemination</p> <p>Once a “final” version is achieved, the guidelines need to be made visible on the project website as well as should be distributed to other stakeholders in each region that are interested and capable to adopt and implement the guidelines by themselves. Each of their experiences in</p>

	<p>deploying the guidelines should also be communicated to BETTER Life, so as to reflect these experiences on the website and in the project reports.</p> <p>Translations</p> <p>To ensure the guideline’s relevancy in each of the partner countries, it should be considered if the guidelines should be translated into the language of each country. Doing so might allow for a wider audience and could ease the target stakeholders into using the guidelines.</p>
<p>How should it look on the website? What format does the tool have?</p>	<p>The guidelines need to be published in a form of a report, together with the reports on users’ experiences and lessons learned.</p>
<p>Key factors for success</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robust design of the guidelines based on the best available science, and careful search for relevant good practices in terms of the evaluation of landscape quality by citizens. • Iterative improvements of the guidelines based on users’ feedback, previous exploitation rounds, taking into account the feedback and opinions of the users. • Carefully designed trial round and broad dissemination.
<p>Implementation field</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trial round in a community with ongoing planning process • Workshops with Project Partners • Workshops with Quadruple Helix Actors • University Lectures or University Seminars • Citizen Science projects • Various stages of the spatial planning process
<p>Other tools suitable for combination</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic Bridge • Mentorship Programme • Visual Methodologies for Landscape Observatory • (Human) Ecosystem Integration Lab: Platform

Toolkit n. 2

Design Thinking for Co-design Public Open Spaces

Type:	Guidelines
Matching Standard(s)	1.2, 1.3, 2.2, 3.3
Responsibility:	UNICAM
Authors:	Samara Ferreira Crispim, Anna Rita Emili, Valentina Polci, Massimo Sargolini, Ana Sopina, Flavio Stimilli

Short description	<p>Designed as a practical guide, the Design Thinking toolkit provides a comprehensive approach to help users overcome challenges and identify opportunities in the co-design of public open spaces. It is based on the principles of Design Thinking and offers a range of strategic tools and actionable steps aimed at delivering integrated solutions through measures that include identifying stakeholders and understanding the needs of the local community. It then guides users through a dynamic process that includes empathy, identification and definition, research and planning, implementation, testing, and evaluation phases. Targeting doctoral candidates, researchers, and professionals working at the intersection of life sciences, urban well-being, and urban planning, the main goal of the toolkit is to enable users to facilitate and optimize co-design processes in close collaboration with local communities and stakeholders. These efforts aim to positively transform the urban environment and improve the quality of urban life.</p>
Target group(s)	<p>The toolkit is tailored for doctoral candidates, researchers, and professionals specializing in urban planning and revitalization, environmental and urban studies, urban well-being, and community-oriented co-design. Moreover, its scope extends to city staff and nonprofit organizations dedicated to enhancing the quality of urban livability within their respective communities.</p>

<p>Benefit for target group(s)</p>	<p>The benefit of the toolkit for the target audience is that it harnesses the versatile and non-traditional problem-solving methods of Design Thinking, which can be applied across a wide range of disciplines and challenges. By applying Design Thinking methods, users acquire holistic skills to identify and solve human-centered challenges, drive innovation, and adapt to different problem-solving scenarios.</p>
<p>Measures</p>	<p>The measures encompass the development of a holistic approach rooted in Design Thinking, emphasizing human-centered design principles for co-designing public open spaces. This approach advocates for a comprehensive assessment of the needs and aspirations of the local community, involving the provision of a range of unconventional tools and strategies to foster the generation of new ideas and concepts across the phases of empathy, identification and definition, research and planning, implementation, testing, and evaluation. In simpler terms, these measures are crafted to facilitate the co-design process and the conversion of novel ideas and concepts into feasible solutions. Additionally, the measures involve the creation of templates and recommendations for documenting the co-design process and its outcomes, facilitating knowledge sharing, and disseminating best practices among professionals and communities.</p>
<p>Expected outcome(s)</p>	<p>The expected outcome is a Design Thinking toolkit that provides a systematic, step-by-step framework for applying Design Thinking to the co-design of public open spaces. It is expected that successful implementation will result in a practical downloadable guide that will serve as a versatile resource for workshops, research endeavors, and real-world projects on the topic addressed. Ultimately, it is expected that effective use of the toolkit will result in tangible improvements in public open spaces through community and stakeholder collaboration while contributing to academic and professional advancement in the realms of co-design, urban planning, and urban well-being.</p>

<p>Specific activities and resources required</p>	<p>Several specific activities are required to develop the Design Thinking toolkit. These include in-depth research on Design Thinking methods, best practices for urban planning and public open spaces, and urban well-being. Relevant content, case studies, and examples will be compiled for the toolkit. A clear framework will be designed to outline the step-by-step co-design process and tools. Content will be created to explain Design Thinking concepts, provide guidance for activities, and engage stakeholders. Templates, worksheets, and tools will be developed for each phase of the Design Thinking process (e.g., empathy maps and brainstorming sheets), for which visually appealing layouts with graphics and diagrams will be designed. In addition, the Design Thinking toolkit will be tested in a small group to gather user feedback. Content will be reviewed and edited for accuracy and accessibility. Finally, formatting and layout will be done for both the printed and digital versions of the Design Thinking toolkit, which will be made available for viewing and downloading on the BETTER Life programme platform or website.</p> <p>Resources required include expertise in Design Thinking, urban planning, and content development; access to research materials such as academic papers and case studies; use of content creation tools, graphic design, and user testing; and sufficient time and staff for research, development, and refinement.</p>
<p>How should it look on the website? What format does the tool have?</p>	<p>The presentation of the Design Thinking toolkit on the website should be visually appealing and organized for easy navigation and use. It should begin with an introduction to its purpose and benefits, and then be divided into user-friendly sections, each corresponding to a phase of the Design Thinking process. Therefore, it can be made available on the website as a practical guide with the possibility to download tools, templates sheets, and resources for each phase. Offering the toolkit in both an interactive digital format and a printable PDF format would enhance the user experience and meet multiple needs, users could access additional reading materials and support. In addition, the website design should</p>

	<p>ensure a seamless user experience and feature consistent imagery.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Template sheets for use in the co-design processes • Links to possible (open access) tools to implement engagement of stakeholders into co-design process
Key factors for success	<p>The success of the toolkit relies on key elements that enhance its effectiveness and widespread use. These factors encompass a solid foundation in Design Thinking principles, fostering empathy and innovation, as well as stakeholder engagement and community participation, which play a pivotal role in ensuring that diverse perspectives shape the co-design process. The practical guide, along with digital and printable resources, caters to different user types, thereby promoting learning and the sharing of ideas. Its clear communication and user-friendly templates are also key factors contributing to its success, as they facilitate understanding and application. In essence, the toolkit's success thrives on its holistic, user-centered, and collaborative approach, built upon practical resources, effective communication, and an unwavering commitment to ongoing improvement.</p>
Implementation field	<p>The implementation field entails the practical realization and execution of participatory co-design processes for public open spaces in urban, peri-urban and extra-urban (rural) contexts (e.g., green spaces and public squares). This includes translating collaborative ideas and concepts into tangible, functional, and aesthetically pleasing physical spaces that meet the needs and aspirations of local communities and stakeholders.</p>
Other tools suitable for combination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting Interaction of Community, Science, and Governance • Promote Your Research Communication • Visual Methodologies for Landscape Observatory

Toolkit n. 3

Promote your Research Communication

Type: Guidelines

Matching Standard(s) 2.3, 4.2

Responsibility: EDUCONS

Authors: Gordana Racic, Andrea Andrejević Panić

<p>Short description</p>	<p>This toolkit would be comprising user-friendly guidelines designed to assist researchers in promoting their findings, primarily through social media. The guidelines would offer best practices for creating engaging posts, selecting appropriate channels, leveraging visual aids, using keywords or hashtags for increased visibility, and tailoring communication for diverse audiences</p>
<p>Target group(s)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early career researchers • Institution (teaching and research staff)
<p>Benefit for target group(s)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greater relevance, accountability and transparency of research outcomes • Making ECR research more visible in the field • Enhance reputation and impact of research • Opportunity in obtaining research fundings • Reaching the stakeholders • Informing, raising awareness of science-related topics • Getting involved with audiences including people from outside the science community • Science embedded in the daily life
<p>Measures</p>	<p>Guideline will be formed of two chapters: academic communication and public communication</p> <p>Main contents of the guideline will include</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Steps to be undertaken before publication (Keywords, title, and abstract, Journal search, ORCID profile) • Promote you research (social media promotion (Twitter, ResearchGate, Academia, ScienceOpen, My Science Work), videos creation, graphical abstracts, promotion at conferences, data sharing, email signature, blogging, press

	<p>release)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring of the impact (Almetrics) • Identification of stakeholders relevant for the field of the research
Expected outcome(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing research visibility • Widening opportunities for fundings, trainings, workshops • Use of institutional repository for supporting open science • Long term positive effects of scientific results and achievements • Improvement of goals or focus of the research • Bringing citizens closer to science (research outputs) • Influencing people's attitudes and behaviors
Specific activities and resources required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mentorship programme informed • Visibility on the website of the institution • Use of digital technologies for methodologies such as storytelling, persuasion etc.
How should it look on the website? What format does the tool have?	<p>Tool will be in the form of the interactive tool on the website which will lead each user to the written Guidelines which will include previously published links and videos will be attached</p>
Key factors for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detailed information given in the Guideline • Promote Guideline to the ECR through website of institution, and other tools (Mentorship programme, Academic Bridge) • Research that is responsive to societal needs and interests
Implementation field	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide to ECR with company profile cards where they can promote their research • Provide ECR with trainings on how to promote their research • Supporting institutional repository
Other tools suitable for combination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting Interaction of Community, Science and Governance • Academic Bridge • Mentorship programme

Toolkit n. 4

Educative Boardgame / Roleplay Game

Type:	Training
Matching Standard(s)	2.1, 2.2
Responsibility:	MLU
Authors:	Arjan de Groot, Susanne Winge, Anton Shkaruba

<p>Short description</p>	<p>A serious, educative board- or roleplay game that allows participants to better understand the need for and advantages of collaboration amongst Quadruple Helix actors. The game focuses on teaching the importance of engaging science and cooperative initiatives to address and manage societal and environmental challenges.</p> <p>The players, ideally represented by actors related to Quadruple Helix stakeholders, assume the role of a number of different entities within the game scenario. As part of the game, each player will have their own targets, while also striving to cooperate with other players to reach shared and communal goals. Failure to reach communal or shared goals will have negative consequences for all participants, but they each need to finely balance how much of their resources are allocated towards their own agenda and how much they want to contribute to common targets.</p> <p>The game will have a certain duration, likely tied to development goals existing in the EU policy framework and will thus be played in rounds, whereby each round represents a certain timeframe. The game ends after a certain timeframe has crossed, after which communal and individual goals will be evaluated to determine who managed to allocate their resources most efficiently.</p>
<p>Target group(s)</p>	<p>Early Career Researcher (ECR)</p> <p>As defined in the BETTER Life proposal. The game can be tailored to and played exclusively by ECR, allowing them to gain valuable insight into the needs and operative procedures of Quadruple Helix actors. It is intended that, after playing the game, ECR can better judge how to engage certain stakeholders, how to connect with them on the topic</p>

	<p>of shared challenges and who might be a strong ally in their research.</p> <p>University Members</p> <p>Due to the game’s focus on educative purposes and its highlight on socially engaged research, the game is well suited to practical lessons in many different university lecture topics. It is likely that the game will be tested, refined and improved based on feedback received by students from project partner universities.</p> <p>Quadruple Helix Actors</p> <p>As defined in the BETTER Life proposal. Due to its inherent nature of reinforcing the idea of cooperation and collaboration, the game is excellently suited for workshops or meetings involving representatives of multiple or all Quadruple Helix sectors. Playing the game will allow those representatives to gain a better understanding of each actors focal areas, as well as where potential areas for alignment may lie.</p>
<p>Benefit for target group(s)</p>	<p>Early Career Researcher (ECR)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A better understanding of the intricate needs and agendas of various societal, industrial and institutional stakeholders. • A better understanding of the various approaches and targets at play, allowing ECR to better frame their research and ensure its viability in terms of implementation on the ground. • Design of possible research topics that are of interest to all Quadruple Helix actors, as well as determining which topics might be more challenging to implement. • A better overview of how Quadruple Helix actors judge, engage with and address certain societal challenges. <p>University Members</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A tool to interactively design a practical seminar during their lecture series. • An engaging way to teach young students about various goals, agendas and individual targets among important and influential societal stakeholders.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A fun way to teach the importance of collaboration and cooperation, while also highlighting the inherent need of certain stakeholders to prioritise their own gains and targets, thus providing a realistic reflection of the various influences at play in a community. <p>Quadruple Helix Actors</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A tool to highlight the importance of maintain good relations with other Quadruple Helix actors to achieve their own targets. • A better understanding of the need for collaborating on achieving, mitigating or addressing certain societal challenges, as failure to do so can present significant losses to one’s own institution. • An engaging and realistic representation of striving towards the achievement of societal goals, while also maintaining their own ambitions and targets. • A first step towards more collaborative efforts due to the lessons learned from the game and the understanding gained on the effects of not fulfilling societal goals. • A better understanding of how serious games can help bring actors and stakeholders together to unite in an attempt to address certain societal challenges.
Measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of the Game will be based on input from students, as well as input from stakeholders approached in earlier stages of the project. Doing so will ensure that the game remain relevant to important topics in the project regions and that the needs and ambitions of certain stakeholders are adequately captured and represented. • The game will be played in iterations during workshops with BETTER Life partners, during University lecture series and during workshops with Quadruple Helix actors. Each iteration will likely lead to a refinement and improvement of the game, until its final version.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To ensure the game is appealing and fun to play, a graphics designed will be involved in creating tokens, a board, playing figures, stakeholder cards and other visual necessities for the game.
<p>Expected outcome(s)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Once the final version of the game is reached, it will be made publicly available on the BETTER Life project website as well as be made available to stakeholders that cooperate and have engaged with BETTER Life. As such, the game will be disseminated to the wider public and can reach as many stakeholders as possible. Feedback surveys of players of the game will be conducted after the game has been played. Players of the game will be asked about a number of topics, such as experience playing the game, improvements to be made, missing or misrepresented aspects, etc. It is expected that the game provides its players with a fun and interactive experience that also teaches and highlights the importance of collaboration to achieve societal goals. Despite the focus on engaging and collaborative actions, the game will also provide a realistic experience in that each player will have their own agenda and will need to, at times, prioritise this agenda in the way their resources are allocated.
<p>Specific activities and resources required</p>	<p>Workshops To design the game and create a robust ruleset while also ensuring that the collaborative aspect in the game shines through, while also providing sufficient focus on individual goals.</p> <p>Physical representation of the game Once the ruleset and design of the game is finished, great care should be taken to design the visual representation of the game. A board, playing figures, dice, cardsets etc. need to be developed and should be designed well enough to create a visually appealing appearance.</p> <p>Feedback Surveys and Refinement Once the game is played in testing rounds, surveys need to be prepared and subsequently distributed to the players to collect feedback. Based on this feedback, the game</p>

	<p>can be refined and improved upon.</p> <p>Dissemination Once a “final” version is achieved, the game needs to be made visible on the project website as well as should be distributed to other stakeholders in each region that are interested and capable to adopt and implement the game by themselves. Each of their experiences in playing the game should also be communicated to BETTER Life, so as to reflect these experiences on the website and in the project reports.</p> <p>Translations To ensure the game’s relevancy in each of the partner countries, it should be considered if the game should be translated into the language of each country. Doing so might allow for a wider audience and could ease the target stakeholders into playing the game. Playing the game in English might create aversion and hesitancy.</p>
<p>How should it look on the website? What format does the tool have?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The game will likely be played as a boardgame while also making extensive use of events, action cards and influence points. The game will be played in person and should not take longer than an hour. • On the website, pictures of the game, its rules and playing tools (dice, cards, figures) can be presented – as well as experiences and lessons learned from previous playing rounds.
<p>Key factors for success</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective outreach and consultation of ECR, students and Quadruple Helix actors. • The game needs to be sufficiently complex, but also easy to learn and play. It cannot be too long (1h max). • The board, tokens, cards etc. need to be of good quality and great design to enhance the gaming experience. • Iterative improvements to the game based on previous playing rounds, considering the feedback and opinions of previous players. • Successful communication of the game’s rules and its teaching values to other actors that might implement and adopt the game in their approach regarding socially engaged research and practices.

Implementation field	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Workshops with Project Partners• Workshops with Quadruple Helix Actors• University Lectures or University Seminars• Citizen Science projects• Schools
Other tools suitable for combination	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Promote your Research Communication• Academic Bridge• Mentorship Programme• Visual Methodologies for Landscape Observatory• (Human) Ecosystem Integration Lab: Platform

Toolkit n. 5

SER Self-Reflection Tool

Type:	Platform
Matching Standard(s)	1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 3.1, 3.2, 4.1, 4.2, 4.3
Responsibility:	ACEEU
Author:	Lina Landinez

Short description	BL-Social Engaged Research (SER) is a self-reflection tool for early career researchers (ECR) who wish to explore, understand and develop their engaging activity and potential with societal actors (including skills, knowledge, behaviour, etc.), especially non-academic audiences. It guides them through a process of identification, prioritisation and action planning in specific key areas. It diagnoses areas of strength and weakness, opens up discussion on the engagement efforts and allows to track evolution over time
Target group(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ECR in life sciences
Benefit for target group(s)	<p>The BL-SER self- reflection tool is a clear framework to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand what is required to be engaged in research • Analyse the individual level and nature of engagement • Get recommendations for individuals aiming to improve their activity and exploit their potential engagement in research • Communicate to others their efforts and achievement in engagement • Develop your path to improve their engagement in research
Measures	<p>Using the HEI Innovate self-assessment tool as a reference point and based on the BL standards, we will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapt the dimensions to an individual level and tailor to engagement. • Adjust the eight dimensions of HEI Innovate to the BETTER Life ones. • Adapt the questions per dimension. Each dimension has a short description and is followed by a series of questions the answers use a scale, eg. from 0 to 5.

	<p>Each answer can have an explanation or example to make it easier to understand</p>
<p>Expected outcome(s)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have a self- reflection tool designed for individuals to analyse their engagement activity and potential. • Provide a tool to assess and monitor efforts in the engagement of researchers. • Support the development of engagement activities for researchers.
<p>Specific activities and resources required</p>	<p>Development:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outlining the scope and timeline of the platform development. <p>Platform:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defining the concept and design of the platform. • Defining the web page requirements. • Determining the features and functionalities, including questions, answer options, results. <p>Content:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designing the content • Uploading the content <p>Implementation and Pilot:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementing the plan and developing the platform. • Testing the platform. Pilot version. • Adjusting the platform. <p>Launch:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporate the platform (web-based) into the BL website. • Feedback from users to the platform can be part of the BL website. <p>Using the platform:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Home page: once register, there will be a dashboard with the option to start a new test and the tests the user has taken • Self-reflection: the questionnaire starts with the first dimension. Each dimension is an independent page and answers. Flexibility of fill in the questionnaire • Results: once finalised, the answers are submitted and will be displayed graphically according to the scores

How should it look on the website? What format does the tool have?	Web-based platform <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Design of the platform is to be decided and aligned to BL, it will be as a user-friendly and visually appealing online space (tab in the BL website)• Login/Registration: ask for user to register with minimal personal information
Key factors for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Easy to understand for users (user experience): filling in time is efficient, questions are relatable to users,• Positive feedback evaluation• Use together with other tools (e.g. mentorship programme, self-assessment tool)
Implementation field	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• ECR in life sciences at the universities and institutional structures supporting them in their research projects• integration in the BL Winter and Summer School
Other tools suitable for combination	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• BL self-assessment tool (WP4)• Mentorship programme

Toolkit n. 6

Visual Methodologies for Landscape Observatory

Type:	Guideline
Matching Standard(s)	1.2, 1.3, 2.1, 2.2, 2.3
Responsibility:	UNICAM
Authors:	Anna Rita Emili, Valentina Polci, Salvatore Santuccio, Massimo Sargolini, Ana Sopina, Flavio Stimilli

<p>Short description</p>	<p>Visual Methodologies for Landscape Observatory is a training course for implementing and utilizing visual toolkits to work and communicate with the community and interested stakeholders on spatial and landscape planning approaches to landscape enhancement and raising the quality of life. It is an approach to unifying the production of art and visual communication methods to scientific production and landscape research.</p> <p>Visual methodologies use various means of artwork as visual presentation tools - photographs, illustrations, pictograms, and drawings as well as storytelling and video materials to engage community and stakeholders in scientific research and landscape planning. The implementation of visual methodologies empower young scientists, the community, and stakeholders to communicate and mutually share their knowledge, ideas, views, and needs on inherited landscape values to foster contextual research of landscape. Visual methodologies contribute to developing the Landscape Observatory framework and widening the Landscape Observatory network.</p> <p>The theoretical framework for the use of visual methodologies is the Landscape Observatory. Landscape Observatory is a network of institutions and stakeholders, a space for experience exchange on the dynamic equilibrium, interactions, and transformations between natural and anthropogenic networks. The concept of landscape is understood as an interaction between natural and cultural</p>
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	<p>networks as well as the interrelation of natural and cultural assets and their context. The spatial scope of Landscape Observatory is oriented on the Mediterranean Europe landscape settings of the intense interaction between coast and inland that include natural connections of river, valley, hill, and mountain habitats and biodiversity to cultural-historical, functional, and symbolical connections.</p> <p>The training course Visual Methodologies for Landscape Observatory is focused on the use of visual arts in developing storytelling of scientific achievement or the metaphoric presentation of research methods or results. The aim is to make communication between local administrators, urban and spatial planners, and the community more friendly and to make the process of analyzing and planning territories more collective.</p>
<p>Target group(s)</p>	<p>The target groups include various stakeholders interested in the topics of territorial planning, enhancement of ecological and societal landscape networks, as well as raising the quality of living:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Young researchers dealing with spatial topics within the life sciences, • Spatial planners, architects, and other professionals involved in the process of planning and analyzing the territory, both in the landscape and in the urban context, • Administrators who want to participate in the planning process of a territory in a collective project, • Community and locally engaged organisations, • Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) active locally.
<p>Benefit for target group(s)</p>	<p>The general benefit to all involved groups is empowerment to communicate their knowledge, ideas, views, and needs on inherited landscape values as well as gathering new knowledge from other groups.</p> <p>The benefit for architects and planners will be double - firstly, they can get more input from the population and all communities involved in the planning, and secondly, they can offer a clearer idea of their design choices during planning development.</p>

	<p>For citizens and administrators, the benefit will be knowledge of the issues involved in the planning process and a more integrated awareness of planning development.</p>
<p>Measures / activities</p>	<p>The aim is to make communication between local administrators, urban and spatial planners, and the community more friendly and to make the process of analyzing and planning territories more collective.</p> <p>The development of a trans-European network of Landscape Observatory answers the need to monitor landscape transformations, analyse new ways of establishing coastal and inland landscape relations, as well as to exchange experience with institutions and stakeholders active in the field of promoting, evaluating, and governing landscapes. The aim is to create a platform for collecting information about the relation transformations of coastal and inland territories within Mediterranean Europe.</p>
<p>Expected outcome(s)</p>	<p>The main expected result is to organize a virtuous exchange in the territorial planning process, between researchers, planners, administrations, and the population. This exchange, which has not been very linear and participatory up to now, could, through the training of experts specialized in the communication of project analyzes and choices, be an important element of participatory planning and of the sharing by the communities of design choices for their future.</p>
<p>Specific activities and resources required</p>	<p>In order to train experts in communication through visual methodologies, it will be necessary to organize specific workshops, articulated on experimental processes, coordinated by experts in different sectors, from storytelling to videomaking, from photography to ideogrammatic and iconic drawing. These workshops will also be open to observers other than the professionals they are aimed at, to keep an open response to the needs of the broader targets identified by the process, even during the workshop.</p> <p>The tools will be divided into two groups: the first concerns storytelling (with videos, sketches, animated drawings, etc.) to tell the greatest number of users about the designers' choices, overcoming the difficulties of common project</p>

	<p>representations. The second concerns the possibility of asking the population to participate in the analysis and planning of the landscape, making it easier for citizens to contribute (with synthetic diagrams, pictograms, mental maps, impressions, and so on).</p>
<p>How should it look on the website? What format does the tool have?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview of training course summary with training course topics / content and training material. • Links to held / premade classes exploring topics of Visual Methodologies and Landscape Observatory. • The tool can be presented by best practices examples of storytelling, artwork, pictograms that present the application of Visual Methodologies in scientific research and/or communicating to public. • Map of Landscape Observatory network overviewing already included institutions and stakeholders (classification - educational institutions, public agencies, small & medium enterprises (SME), stakeholder organisations...) to promote the Landscape Observatory activities. Invitation to expand the network to all interested parties. • Additional information on Landscape Observatory. • Timeline of planned activities open for scientific / public engagement (possible to develop on the level of all tools and project activities).
<p>Key factors for success</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Originality of using art and visual methodologies as a shared language for planning, observing, understanding cultural and natural landscape • Effective involvement of Quadruple Helix stakeholders in training, so that ECR and others are increasingly able to apply these new forms of communication and coordination • Continually updated best practices so that they inspire and stimulate more friendly communication of landscape practices among researchers, communities, and local government • Living exchange between all stakeholders by using several methods of communication and coordination

Implementation field	Field of territorial planning and spatial topics within the life sciences with the aim of enhancement of ecological and societal landscape networks, as well as raising the quality of living. Implementation regards open public spaces with local communities and stakeholders, in urban, peri-urban, and extra-urban environments focusing on green public areas and places of community as well as ecological importance.
Other tools suitable for combination	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Supporting Interaction of Community, Science, and Governance• Design Thinking• Promote Your Research Communication

Toolkit n. 7

Mentorship Programme

Type:	Platform
Matching Standard(s)	1.1, 1.2, 2.1, 2.2, 4.1
Responsibility:	DU
Author:	Edgar Kucins

Short description	Development of a mentoring toolkit that provides an interactive exchange of knowledge and wisdom between a mentor and a mentee. The exchange through the programme will be facilitated through the creation of a conducive environment for learning and growth. The toolkit will provide mentors with the necessary resources and tools to help and assist mentees and group of mentees to understand, apply and integrate their strengths in their respective roles and scientific fields.
Target group(s)	Doctoral students, recent graduates, interns.
Benefit for target group(s)	Skill development, career guidance, career counseling, networking opportunities, personalized advice, feedback and improvement.
Measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Goal-Setting Frameworks. Provide templates and guidelines for mentors and mentees to collaboratively set clear and achievable goals for the mentoring relationship. • Structured Meeting Formats. Develop structured formats for mentoring meetings, including agendas and topics to cover in each session. • Feedback and Reflection Tools. Provide tools for mentors and mentees to give and receive constructive feedback. • Resource Sharing. Offer a curated list of relevant resources such as articles, videos, online courses, and books that align with the mentee's interests and goals. • Networking Strategies. Provide tips for building professional networks, attending industry events, and

	<p>making meaningful connections within the STEM community.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Success Stories and Case Studies. Include real-life success stories and case studies of mentoring relationships that have led to positive outcomes, inspiring mentees and mentors alike. • Evaluation and Continuous Improvement. Provide tools for mentors and mentees to evaluate the effectiveness of the mentoring relationship and allow for adjustments for ongoing improvement.
Expected outcome(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced Skill Development. Mentees should experience improved technical, problem-solving, and communication skills as a result of guidance and support from their mentors. • Clear Career Pathways. Early career professionals who engage with the toolkit should have a clearer understanding of their career goals and the steps required to achieve them. • Expanded Professional Networks. Mentees can expect to build meaningful connections within their industry through the networking strategies provided in the toolkit. • Long-Term Connections. The toolkit can facilitate the development of lasting connections between mentors and mentees.
Specific activities and resources required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking Events. Organize networking events, webinars, or workshops to facilitate connections between mentees and professionals. • Feedback Sessions. Provide guidelines for mentors and mentees to conduct regular feedback sessions, ensuring that both parties are learning and improving from the relationship. • Guidelines and Frameworks. Provide written guidelines outlining the roles, responsibilities, and expectations of mentors and mentees. • Evaluation Forms. Templates for assessing the effectiveness of the mentoring relationship and identifying areas for improvement.

<p>How should it look on the website? What format does the tool have?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of the services offered through the tool as well as the goals, deliverables and objectives when participating in the programme as both a mentor or a mentee, will be hosted on the BETTER Life website. • Examples and success stories of similar initiatives or already “completed” mentorship programmes to be hosted on the website. • Further information and a means to express interest and sign up to the programme as either a mentor or a mentee.
<p>Key factors for success</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear Objectives and Goals. The toolkit should clearly define the objectives of the mentorship programme and the specific goals that mentors and mentees are expected to work towards. • Regular Communication. Encourage regular and open communication between mentors and mentees, fostering a supportive and collaborative environment. • Flexibility and Adaptability. Recognize that each mentoring relationship is unique. The toolkit should allow for flexibility to accommodate different learning styles, preferences, and goals. • Measurement of Impact. Develop methods for measuring the impact of the toolkit on the professional development and success of mentees, which can help refine the toolkit over time.
<p>Implementation field</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic Institutions. Universities and research institutions can implement the toolkit to facilitate mentorship programmes that connect students with experienced professionals in STEM fields. • Research Organizations. Research-focused institutions can use the toolkit to pair early career researchers with scientists or experts who can guide them in their research endeavours.
<p>Other tools suitable for combination</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic Bridge • Promote your Research Communication

Toolkit n. 8

(Human) Ecosystem Integration Lab

Type: Dedicated tab in the BETTER Life website

Matching Standard(s) 1.1, 1.2, 2.1, 2.2, 4.2

Responsibility: HELIXCONNECT

Author: Emilia Binchiciu

<p>Short description</p>	<p>(Human) Ecosystem Integration Lab will serve as a digital instrument, found within a dedicated tab on the BETTER Life website. This tool is designed for the active participation of Quadruple Helix stakeholders—universities, businesses, administrations, and NGOs—in engaging with the community. Its focus lies in facilitating discussions and collaborations related to research in life sciences.</p> <p>Among the key features of this tab, Quadruple Helix stakeholders, including the ERC (early career researchers), will have the ability to submit concise abstracts with pre-defined keywords associated with their research concepts and areas of interest. Inclusive of functionalities such as a forum, the option to create user profiles (including information such as name, email, affiliation, research field and age), the (H)EIL aims to streamline the ERC's professional growth and advancement within their research career.</p>
<p>Target group(s)</p>	<p>Quadruple Helix stakeholders — universities (ECR), businesses, administrations, and NGOs</p>
<p>Benefit for target group(s)</p>	<p>Efficient Collaboration: enables Quadruple Helix stakeholders to easily connect and collaborate with each other in order to share insights, expertise, and resources, fostering interdisciplinary collaborations that can lead to innovative solutions.</p> <p>Research Dissemination: allows stakeholders to share their research ideas and concepts through short abstracts and keywords which can lead to the rapid dissemination of research topics to a broader audience.</p>

	<p>Enhanced Visibility: Quadruple Helix stakeholders can showcase their expertise and interests through the platform, enhancing their visibility within the community.</p>
<p>Measures</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defining the concept and purpose of the (H)EIL tab. • Determining the features and functionalities of the tab. • Planning the user experience. • Establishing effective communication channels within the platform, such as forums and notifications. • Developing the actual (H)EIL platform according to the planned features and design. • Creating user registration and login systems, ensuring data security and privacy. • Implementing the research showcase functionality for uploading abstracts and keywords. • Building the collaboration hub, including forums and threads for discussions. • Testing the platform's functionality, security, and usability before launch. • Launching the platform and monitoring its usage, engagement, and impact.
<p>Expected outcome(s)</p>	<p>Knowledge Exchange and Learning The platform's forums, discussions, and resources promote knowledge exchange and learning among stakeholders. Researchers can learn from each other's experiences, challenges, and successes, contributing to professional growth.</p> <p>Enhanced Collaboration and Networking (H)EIL aims to facilitate cross-sector collaboration among universities, businesses, administrations, NGOs, and researchers. Stakeholders can connect, share ideas, and form partnerships that lead to innovative research projects, interdisciplinary solutions, and collective impact.</p> <p>Community Impact and Engagement By connecting with NGOs and community representatives, (H)EIL can identify research areas with direct societal impact. Research outcomes can address pressing issues, contributing to community well-being and sustainable development.</p>

<p>Specific activities and resources required</p>	<p>Define tab Requirements <u>Activities:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborate with the consortium to gather users' requirements and preferences (internal surveys). <p><u>Resources:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Task coordinator and team members <p>Define Content <u>Activities:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Select research abstracts and populate the tab with content and users (research abstracts and users). Prepare content for the tabs sections <p><u>Resources:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Task coordinator Content selectors <p>Develop the (H) EIL tab <u>Activities:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop the tabs interface, incorporating the defined design elements and collected content. <p><u>Resources:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Task coordinator and team members CZU/MLU IT team
<p>How should it look on the website? What format does the tool have?</p>	<p><u>How can it look like?</u></p> <p>The (Human) Ecosystem Integration Lab (H)EIL platform can be designed as a user-friendly and visually appealing online space (tab in the BL website).</p> <p>(H) EIL tab: welcoming interface with quick access to login or create an account; (H)EIL branding and navigation options (showcasing recent research, news, and upcoming events).</p> <p>Login/Registration: secure user authentication and registration process.</p> <p>Research Showcase: a section for users to upload research abstracts and associated keywords.</p> <p>Collaboration Hub: Interactive forum for discussions.</p>

	<p>Privacy and Security: clear privacy settings allowing users to control the visibility of their information.</p> <p><u>How is it designed?</u></p> <p>Online Tool and Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tab is developed within the BETTER Life website accessible through standard web browsers. <p>Use of Scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users can rate their satisfaction with different features, ease of navigation, or the quality of interactions. <p>Research Showcase and Collaboration Hub:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the research showcase, users can submit open-ended abstracts about their research projects, highlighting key objectives and findings. • Closed questions can be used to categorize the research under specific topics or fields of interest. • The collaboration hub includes open-ended forum discussions where users can initiate conversations and pose questions.
<p>Key factors for success</p>	<p>Enhanced Collaboration and Networking</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (H)EIL aims to facilitate cross-sector collaboration among universities, businesses, administrations, NGOs, and researchers. • Stakeholders can connect, share ideas, and form partnerships that lead to innovative research projects, interdisciplinary solutions, and collective impact. <p>Knowledge Exchange and Learning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tab's forum and resources promote knowledge exchange and learning among stakeholders. • Researchers can learn from each other's experiences, challenges, and successes, contributing to professional growth. <p>Platform Evolution and Adaptation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on user feedback and evolving research trends, (H)EIL can adapt its features and functionalities to remain relevant and impactful.

Implementation field	(H)EIL tab is designed to cater to Quadruple Helix stakeholders, including universities, businesses, administrations, NGOs, and researchers, who are involved in the life sciences. It aims to facilitate collaboration, knowledge exchange, and engagement within the life sciences research community and foster ECR development in the life science field.
Other tools suitable for combination	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Academic Bridge• SER Self-Reflection Tool• Promote your Research Communication• Supporting Interaction of Community, Science and Governance

Toolkit n. 9

Academic Bridge

Type:	Platform
Matching Standard(s)	1.1, 1.2, 2.1, 2.2, 3.1, 3.2, 4.1, 4.3
Responsibility:	CZU
Authors:	Michael Haman, Patrik Toula, Michal Lošťák, Martin Jankovský, Milan Školník

<p>Short description</p>	<p>The proposed platform is a digital hub (website) designed to foster collaboration between municipalities (initially as stakeholders, with potential to include additional stakeholders operating in Quadruple Helix in the future) and researchers.</p> <p>Furthermore, the platform could serve as the foundation for an insightful academic paper focused on municipalities' willingness to collaborate with academia which would be dedicated to the project. The platform's design could be expanded to accommodate other stakeholders in addition to municipalities, and researchers could be given the capability to propose topics, further enhancing the platform's collaborative aspect. Consequently, it's not merely a matching service but a hub that fosters collective research endeavors.</p>
<p>Target group(s)</p>	<p>Early career researchers – as defined in the BETTER Life proposal. Moreover, the platform will be accessible to all academic researchers and students across various fields of research.</p> <p>Municipalities in all 8 countries of the consortium with potential for expansion to other countries. The initial target group will count all 6 254 municipalities in the Czech Republic which will serve as a pilot to other regions.</p> <p>Potential future expansion and extension: Other stakeholders operating in Quadruple Helix interested in socially engaged research (particularly in life sciences) and wanting to participate and utilize such kind of research.</p>

<p>Benefit for target group(s)</p>	<p>Municipalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to academic expertise and possibilities to consult their problems with academia. Municipalities can access data-driven insights and evidence-based recommendations from researchers, enabling them to make more informed decisions about policies, programmes, and projects. • Solutions to local issues backed by research. • Increased visibility of their challenges within the academic community. • Streamlining the bi-directional knowledge transfer between governance and science and research actors to enable a multi-actor approach to consultancy and problem-solving of local issues. • Innovation Acceleration: Collaboration with researchers can lead to innovative solutions that municipalities might not have otherwise considered. Researchers can bring fresh perspectives and cutting-edge ideas to address complex urban challenges. • Capacity Building: Interacting with researchers can contribute to the professional development of municipal employees. Exposure to research methodologies and problem-solving approaches can enhance the capacity of municipal staff to tackle challenges effectively. <p>Researchers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct insight into the real-world challenges faced by municipalities. Implementing research findings in real-world scenarios offers researchers a chance to validate their theories and models. • Opportunities for impactful and locally engaged research. Collaborating with municipalities provides researchers access to valuable real-world data sets, enriching the quality and relevance of their research. • Platform will showcase researchers' expertise. • Publication Opportunities: Successful collaborations with municipalities can lead to compelling case studies or research papers that can be published. • Enhanced Funding Prospects: Demonstration of real-world impact through collaboration with municipalities can strengthen researchers' grant proposals and funding
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	<p>applications, as funding agencies increasingly emphasize practical applications and societal relevance.</p>
Measures / activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distributing surveys to municipalities to identify research interests and other potential areas of cooperation between academia and municipalities. • Developing a dynamic digital platform (website) with potential login to a members-only area. • Continuously updating the platform to maintain an active database of research interests. • Identifying the research interests of municipalities and governance actors through surveys.
Expected outcome(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of a robust digital platform for sharing research topics and governance actors' queries. • Establishing lasting and meaningful relationships between stakeholder groups. • Increasing the exploitation of research results by governance actors and other stakeholder groups. • Identification and cataloging of pressing research topics from municipalities. • Fostering numerous research collaborations between municipalities and academia. • Creating applied research opportunities between the governance actors and academia.
Specific activities and resources required	<p>Activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey creation: Creating a questionnaire to reach out to municipalities. The idea is to include questions about what issues are acute in the municipality and whether the municipality would like to connect with academics for specific research topics. • E-mail outreach: Reaching out to communities via email to identify potential research interests. The questionnaire would go to the official email address of the municipality (the contact email of municipalities should be publicly available information in every EU country). Alternatively, the outreach could take a different form - approaching specific persons according to different portfolios (in large cities) instead of an email address.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital platform development: Designing a platform to support collaboration between municipalities (as stakeholders) and researchers. • Stakeholder engagement sessions: Publishing data and results from communities to academics, laying the groundwork for possible collaborations between communities and the academy. Questionnaire data (data from specific municipalities with topics they would like to research) will be on a public website - ideally broken down by region and research topic, for example. Based on this, academics will be able to contact relevant stakeholders or vice versa. <p>Resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web development and hosting: Including software developers, designers, quality assurance/testers. • Survey tools • Content creators for platform resources • Legal advisor - to ensure that the platform complies with relevant data protection and privacy laws and to draft necessary terms of use and agreements (this will apply to the entire DCoE). • Project and data management
Key factors for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective outreach resulting in active participation from municipalities. • The platform's user-friendliness, coupled with its relevance to the needs of both municipalities and researchers. • Sustained engagement and regular updates to ensure the platform remains dynamic and up to date. • Examples of good practice / Promotion of success stories
Implementation field	Digital collaboration and research platform; partnerships between stakeholders (municipalities) and academia.
Other tools suitable for combination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote your Research Communication • Educative Boardgame/ Role Play-Game • SER Self-Reflection Tool • (Human) Ecosystem Integration Lab

Toolkit n. 10 Stakeholder Specific Interactive Web-based Tool using the R Shiny App

Type:	Platform
Matching Standard(s)	1.2, 1.2, 2.1, 2.2, 4.1
Responsibility:	PULS
Authors:	Viktoria Takacs, Ewelina Marek-Andrzejewska, Piotr Tryjanowski, Michael Haman, Patrik Toula, Michal Lošťák, Martin Jankovský

Short description	<p>Working on the edge of several disciplines (in case of SER in LS sociology, life sciences, human sciences, natural sciences, agriculture, forestry etc..) one can often notice, that there is a lack of available common statistical, and/ or presentation skills appropriate for the data.</p> <p>R shiny application makes it possible to create an interactive web surface which makes it possible to interpret, show, figure and analyse data without specific knowledge in R, C+, Python or other programmes. This is a tool, that makes possible to prepare quick data analysis, and interpretation, or explanatory data analyses. However, for scientific papers, there is a necessity for further – more detailed analysis with some statistical programmes.</p> <p>We will collect appropriate already existing shiny examples, and develop own shiny apps, that can be useful for SER in LS. These web based apps will be hosted on the project website, and will offer ECR an easy tool for interpreting, presenting and analysing their data and also provides help in communication with stakeholders during socially engaged research.</p> <p>This tool aims at providing some basic ideas, on how to start analysing different types of data in SER.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We will provide shiny surfaces in order to demonstrate the proper presentation of continuous-, discrete - and interval data types, texts, geo-tagged data, etc. • The differences between visual communication
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	<p>appropriate in scientific and popular use and give some templates for best ways and potential pitfalls in data presentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R shiny is especially powerful in explanatory data analysis (EDA), which can be useful during the co-creating process of ECR and Quadruple Helix actors. <p>Tool development will be conducted before and during the bootcamps. Some of the apps will be prepared before the bootcamps, and tested during the workshops, moreover, we leave space for further ideas in case more ideas appear during the bootcamps and workshops.</p> <p>Within this tool we will also give further directions, for deeper proper analysis of data for scientific purposes. As there are many published material concerning statistics and data management, we aim to give some basic links to R Packages and adequate literature, rather, than describing the methods.</p>
Target group(s)	<p>Early carrier researchers who would like to analyse data and publish scientific articles within SER.</p>
Benefit for target group(s)	<p>Easier data analyses, some immediate possibility to start for searching the ways of analyses. Additionally, the possibility of thinking about how to analyse the data can shape data collection methods – preferably during the planning phase of socially engaged research.</p>
Measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect already existing shiny apps (freeware) that can be useful for SER in LS. • Prepare own apps in case they are needed for the above mentioned purposes. • Test the web based surfaces during the bootcamp sessions. • Screen for new ideas with the help of ECR and actors within the bootcamp sessions and workshops.
Expected outcome(s)	<p>Easier data analyses, and maybe help in planning (knowledge on what sort of data can be expected in what forms for analyses), help in data presentation and interpretation. Co-creation process of the tool gives an opportunity to make bootcamps more interactive.</p>

<p>Specific activities and resources required</p>	<p>Activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Literature search on the use of already existing shiny apps in life sciences or in SER. • Create the web based shiny surface • Testing the app during the bootcamps; with the data of the participants • Improving the app in co-creation with the participants <p>Resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programme development and hosting: Including software developers, designers, quality assurance/testers • For testing: Any computer with internet access, some data (preferably from the ECR participants of the bootcamp), basic knowledge of Excel tables and statistics.
<p>How should it look on the website? What format does the tool have?</p>	<p>We will provide examples on our BL-website. Moreover, the R shiny web platform will be created.</p>
<p>Key factors for success</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gained expertise in data presentation and management. • Better and quicker data presentation for ECR during the communication with stakeholders.
<p>Implementation field</p>	<p>SER research in life sciences – we can add link to our compendium on all of our workshops or we can also prepare a specific lecture on methodology possibilities.</p>
<p>Other tools suitable for combination</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual Methodologies for Landscape Observatory

3. CONCLUSIONS

The objective of this report was to describe the toolkits for socially engaged research in life sciences within the scope of the BETTER Life project. The toolkits were identified and elaborated through a comprehensive approach that integrated desk research of possible examples and references with a collaborative two-stage methodology featuring co-creation workshops conducted among consortium partners.

In the first workshop, consortium partners identified a shortlist of toolkits (approximately 30 examples) corresponding to and matching the previously defined SER framework and standards. In the second workshop, the partners selected 10 toolkits out of the preliminary list, which were refined and validated one by one. The final toolkits were then developed by small groups of project partners who were involved in each of them with different responsibilities (leader or contributor).

Each toolkit is matching one or more standards and will provide ECR and Quadruple Helix actors with a set of informative and interactive tools to implement impactful research, promote communication amongst the actors involved and thus foster engaging and responsible social research in life sciences. Digital centres of excellence will be established in the research regions through which the various toolkits will be developed, managed and implemented in cooperation with relevant stakeholders in the region.

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REFERENCES

Hisschemoller et al, 2022, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2022.104021>)

